
ЕТНОЛІНГВІСТИКА. ЛІНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГІЯ

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THE LINGUO-ETHNIC CODE OF LANGUAGE PERSONALITY IN THE STUDY OF LANGUAGE INTELLECTUALIZATION

The article is devoted to the peculiarities of objectivization of personality's conceptual picture of the world by the means of linguo-mental capacity in terms of language intellectualization.

Relevance of the research is determined by the need to clarify an issue of language national identity, within the intellectual evolution of lingual paradigms of knowledge, as one of the most actual constituent of contemporary anthropological approach.

The purpose of the present paper is to determine the nature of implementation the language personality through lingual interiorization of reality on the matter of language intellectual evolution.

As the investigation reveals, correlation peculiarities between notions «language personality» and «language intellectualization» occur in the field of implementation the aesthetical resource and rational capacity of language units with significant semantic content (cultural, historyosophical, philosophical, linguosophical), motivated by contextual words and phrasal environment. It expounds the language intellectual evolution as a process of objectifying new knowledge with language symbols, that are reviewed not as motivated by inductive principle of consequence but through individual interpretation and recontextualization of the idea of initial input reality.

Key words: *linguo-ethnic code, language personality, language intellectualization, language picture of the world, mentality.*

Агібалова Т. М. *Лінгвоетнічний код мовної особистості в теорії інтелектуалізації мови.* У статті досліджено особливості об'єктивзації в мовній картині світу ментальних засад особистості з огляду на теорію інтелектуалізації мови. Ідею пізнання культури через мову окреслено в проєкції на цивілізаційно-естетичні парадигми національного світобачення. Лінгвальну актуалізацію поняття менталітету розглянуто як форму мовної маніфестації світоглядної концепції індивіда. Окреслено змістове поле еволюційних зрушень літературної мови на сучасному етапі в межах ключових акцентів наукового дискурсу інтелектуалізації.

Ключові слова: *лінгвоетнічний код, мовна особистість, інтелектуалізація мови, мовна картина світу, ментальність.*

Агібалова Т. Н. *Лингвоэтнический код языковой личности в теории интеллектуализации языка.* В статье проанализированы особенности объективации в языковой картине мира ментальных основ личности. Идея познания культуры посредством языка описана в проекции на цивилизационно-эстетические парадигмы национального образа мышления. Лингвальную актуализацию понятия менталитета рассмотрено как форму языковой манифестации мировоззренческой концепции индивида. Определено содержательное поле эволюционных процессов в литературном языке на современном этапе в рамках ключевых акцентов научного дискурса интеллектуализации.

Ключевые слова: *лингвоэтнический код, языковая личность, интеллектуализация языка, языковая картина мира, ментальность.*

Language system as a correlate of mentality subsists in discourse of cultural background and social context. In terms of intellectualization study, it is always motivated by world view peculiarities at any stage of human development. Therefore, language personality is revealed through a set of expressive means in everyday communicative practice that distinguishes one individual from other ethnic features keepers. The prominent concernment occurs in the field of individual recontextualization of the commonly used language units' meaning and application, that reflect the national picture of the world, but being reconstructed, at the same time, in a creator's individualized language performance by the means of intellectual capacity.

Analysis of lingualized ideological preferences enables us to comprehend the nature of historical paradigms of cognition, accommodated to ethnic background, the ability to indicate the convention of philosophical thought and cultural development, regarding to the history of world civilizations. Remodeled in every language cognition, the following complex of factors implies a progression of language enrichment and intellectualization.

At the present stage of linguistics and cognitive linguistics study the problem of linguo-ethnic code as means of nature, assimilation and use of knowledge transferring is one of the most actual issue. Researchers offer the three directions of study to define their character of interrelation: 1) investigation the types of knowledge, presented in language symbols, and discovering a mechanisms of knowledge obtaining; 2) analysis of language symbols origin and development, and understanding regulating laws and conditions of their applying; 3) detection link lines between language symbols and cultural realities they reflect [2; 3; 4; 5; 7].

In theoretical and practical context, the following issue is investigated as the most multifaceted aspect of current philological study. From this perspective, the series of linguistics research on cognitive models of humans' ideological paradigms, on language as a mediator of aesthetical resource become the most significant. The intellectual progress in language is seen as condition of its existence, as cognitive resource, as a key factor in its cultural codes conformation (A. Wierzbicka, G. Lakoff, L. Talmy, W. Chafe, N. Arutyunova, L. Shevchenko, S. Yermolenko, L. Lysychenko, Y. Karpenko, K. Goloborodko, O. Malenko, A. Taranenko, O Selivanova, L. Matsko). The problem of investigation of language national identity, within the intellectual evolution of lingual paradigms of knowledge, remains one of the most relevant point for research. Therefore, the purpose of present paper is to clarify the nature of implementation the language personality through lingual interiorization of reality in terms of language intellectual evolution.

Traditionally, ethnic self-identity of individual is connected with detection of the level of intellectual capacity, communication skills acquisition, and gained through the whole life cultural development. These categories are engaged in the mental space formation, that is dynamic form of experience, objectified in evolution of existing civilization values in conditions of intellectual activity. Linguistic format of the concept of mentality transfers an idea of language memory. Outlined in terms of linguistic thought, the theory of comprehending culture through language acquisition is applied by the means of conceptual and language world view.

The space of national picture of the world is formed by a system of symbolic representations of meanings. Verbalized symbols evolve in time and space of culture that defines coordinates and patterns of languages functioning, such as civilizational, aesthetic, idiostylistic factors. Progress and regression in the national language are motivated by stadial change of culture, and intellectualization of symbolic forms defines vectors of development from specific associative categories to the universal abstract forms.

Therefore, mental forms of personal identity represented by the means of cultural memory are defined as compositions of evolutionary transformed symbols that «remember» or «remodel» culture. Language forms of mentality reveal the inherent peculiarities of intellection in the development of lingual mind from nomination to the symbol, from physically appointed picture of reality to the structured semantic and conceptual paradigms.

Intellectual capacity of national language personality regards a concept that defines a set of capabilities and characteristics of a person who creates and receives texts. These peculiarities and characteristics are reflected in communication process. Therefore, language personality designates and measures social, ethnic, cultural, psychological, aesthetic formats, as with every newly-created verbal interpretation germinates further shades of language dimensions. Applying means of national experience, spirits and wisdom in non-predictable circumstances; recognizing guiding organizational principles of language as communicative tool; reproducing mental content and comprehending the structure of expressed ideas; originating, integrating, and combining single speech intentions and ideas into more complicated units in order to produce new patterns or structures; making language choices based on reasoned argument and the value of the evidence, language personality provides the implementation of important practical output in national communicative discourse. The following abilities emphasize the issue of extremely importance of accomplishing a co-called balance between language as concerned with conveying information and language as more inter-personally oriented matter. Appropriately, the concept of language picture of the world requires a comprehensive study of its individual settings and items. For the first time, it was described by Humboldt in his work «On the differences in human languages structure and their influence on the spiritual development of mankind». According his vision, language takes active part in important manifestations of cultural discourse and interpretation of the reality. «Language in accordance with the considered conception, is a universal form of the initial conceptualization of the world, expresser and safe-keeper of unconscious, spontaneous knowledge on the world, historical memory on the socially meaningful events in the human life. Language is a mirror of culture reflecting the images of passed culture, intuition and categories of world outlook» [8].

Evolving in this cultural discourse, intellectual capacity of language personality determines the character of reality interiorization. Since the word is a tool and means of understanding the intellectual meaning of any reality, considering it a mediator of the aesthetical meaning enables identification of intellectualism as one of the key features of speech. According L. Shevchenko, conceptuality of the theory of literary language intellectualization is established as based on the synthesis of

linguistic and epistemological knowledge, due to lingual objectivity, and offered as: 1) dynamics of the literary language evolution in historical and psychological chronotropic guidelines with a prevalence of inherently defined peculiarities and functions; 2) theoretical paradigms transformation given as ordered system of knowledge of the language, its status, functions and further development; 3) theoretical and epistemological methods of investigation: correlation of linguistic knowledge with anthropologically oriented interpretive methodologies of modern science. Therefore, intellectual capacity determines linguistic experience, its encoding in the form of language and mental symbolism [7: 127].

For our research, in terms of psycholinguistics, the fundamental idea of intellect emerges as a representation of the universal structured system of linguistic symbols which evolve in ethnic culture space, form its integrity, continuity and the ability to interpret the mental consciousness. Lingualization of mental experience defines dimension of intellectualization existence. F. Batsevych notes that this kind of reversal of philosophical points of view, exposing nature of lingual reality, provides specific images of language in scientific study. Thus, within the linguistic nature of language comprehension, there are two polar opposite approaches: 1) inherent and semiological (language is considered as itself and for itself); 2) anthropological (within that approach language is motivated in the context of human mind boundaries) [1: 27]. Therefore, language intellectualism criteria are seen as the interrelation of thinking and communicative performance and reflects the human inner sense of language.

However, not any actualized in language form combination of facts may be innovative, not every innovation is a contribution in the process of intellectualization. As analysis reveals, lingual symbols with significant meaning capacity (cultural, historyosophical, philosophical, linguosophical), motivated by contextual words and phrases environment, aestheticize speech, so we consider them the most representative means of intellectualization,

The character of current language intellectualization advance depends on causes and sources of accretion and combines linguo-external and linguo-internal reasons: 1. Every epoch introduces not only novel words but new notions to be denoted. 2. As a basis and, at the same time, result of human intellectual activity literary developed language tends to completely perform the variety of functional styles. 3. Innovations fill in existent lexical, phraseological and stylistic lacunae. 4. Common and terminological lexicons, professional language cliches within certain language community come into usage, following the models of current language development and organization. 5. New dictionaries and reference books officialize up-to-date set of language units. Revealed in scientific research articles, novel approaches to linguistic study offer innovative ways and mechanisms of language standardization. 6. Particular part of language units originate from foreign languages. 7. Individual contextual applications are carried from author's idyostyle. 8. Certain lexemes, providing extension capacity, denote concepts, ideas, or signs as a result of metaphorical nomination. 9. Due to current worldwide tendency of globalization, notions of different spheres tend to contiguity, therefore standardized forms of certain lingual symbols acquire novel meaning shades.

To sum up, we state that interrelation between notions *language personality* and *language intellectualization* occurs in the field of implementation the aesthetical resource and rational capacity of language units with significant semantic content (cultural, historyosophical, philosophical, linguosophical), motivated by contextual word and phrasal environment. It expounds the language intellectual evolution as a process of objectifying new knowledge with language symbols, that is collected and structured not as motivated by inductive principle of consequence but through interpretation and recontextualization of initial input reality.

A detailed study of language personality, manifested in individual literary styles, requires further investigation in terms of the theory of language intellectualization and outlines a perspective of research.

ЛІТЕРАТУРА

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